

**A CRITICAL ASSESSMENT OF SELECTED PRIVATE AND PUBLIC SECTOR BANKS
THROUGH ASSET LIABILITY MANAGEMENT**

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Abstract: Asset-Liability Management (ALM) is a risk management technique used by banks and financial institutions to earn profits return while maintaining an appropriate balance between assets and liabilities. The major types of risks faced by banks are interest rate risk, liquidity risk, credit risk and market risk. The main aim of this study is to analyse the selected 2 public and 2 private commercial banks using Maturity Gap Analysis Model. The analysis shows the highest mismatch ratio is 4.66 of Axis Bank for the maturity bucket of over 3 years and up to 5 years while ICICI Bank is having a mismatch ratio of 4.18 in the short duration bucket of 1 day. The public sector bank SBI has a mismatch ratio of 1.88 followed by PNB with 1.55 mismatch ratio in the maturity bucket of over 1 year and up to 3 years.

Keywords: Asset Liability Management, Gap analysis, Axis Bank, ICICI Bank, SBI, Rate Sensitive Assets.

INTRODUCTION

Banking Industry:

The banking sector of any country plays an important role in its development and growth. A strong banking system plays a significant role in maintaining financial stability by mobilization of deposits and disbursement of loans to the different sectors of the economy.

The financially stable banks protect us against all types of monetary risks. The banking industry in India has undergone many changes since liberalization like generating income through a variety of activities other than the core banking activities, introduction of innovative banking products and services, new opportunities. The deregulation in banking industry with respect to interest rates has also opened up new areas for banks to increase revenues with greater competition, reduced margins and greater risks.

Financial stability can be also be managed with best Asset Liability Management practices. Asset-liability management is the practice of managing bank balance sheet in order manage interest rate and liquidity risks.

Banking business is exposed to credit, market, operational liquidity, interest rate risks with respect to asset-liability management. With the integration of Indian domestic markets with global markets, the risks associated with banks' operations have been increasing and requires strategic management. Indian financial markets have been changing at a fast pace over the last two decades. Increased competition for business concerning both assets and liabilities, with fluctuating interest rates in both domestic and foreign exchange rates has brought pressure on the management of banks to preserve a sufficient balance among spreads, profitability and long-term viability.

The aim of ALM is to manage the risk cordially between risk, liquidity and profitability. With growing

volatility in interest rates markets and cut-throat competition in fund formation, the banks are focusing on managing funds and monitoring the deposit value and the structure of non-deposit liabilities. With the increased use of technology and computing power in the banks, ALM has a broader function to perform.

Asset Liability Management:

Asset Liability Management (ALM) is a tool that helps in calculating, supervising and handling the market risk of a bank. It is also the management of balance sheet (liabilities and assets) in a manner that the net income from interest remains within the preferred risk range. It is about managing balance sheet strategically involving risks which are affected by changes in interest rates, credit risk and the liquidity position of bank.

As financial intermediaries, banks accept deposit to lend money to various sectors of the economy to make profit. They act as an intermediary between depositors and borrowers meeting their liquidity needs and also function with an embedded mismatch between highly liquid liabilities and less liquid and long-term assets of the balance sheets. At the same time they are also exposed to a wide variety of risks like legal risk, liquidity risk, operation risk, reputational risk, interest rate risk, market risk, transformation risk, credit risk, forex risk, etc. The management of 3 major risk i.e., Interest Rate Risk, Liquidity Risk and Credit Risk gave birth to Asset Liability Management.

Risks involved:

The primary motive of the Asset/Liability Management (ALM) Policy is to maximize earnings and return on assets within acceptable levels of risk:

Interest Rate - The interest rate risk is the variation in the price of stock indexes, bonds and other investments that could happen as a result of fluctuation.

Liquidity – The liquidity risk is defined as the inability of the potential to produce adequate cash to deal with the reduction in the deposits or with the growth in the assets.

Capital risk -. Capital risk is the risk an investor faces that he or she may lose all or part of the principal amount invested. It is the risk a company faces that it may lose value on its capital.

Market risk – “The market risk has a connection with the financial condition that is an outcome from the opposing movements in the market prices. This will be more affirmed when the financial data has to be furnished on a market-to-market basis as the important and the constant unpredictable changes in the holdings of an asset could oppose and affect the bank’s balance sheet.” (BIS, n.d.)

Risk Management Techniques involved in ALM:

“Gap analysis model: The gap analysis model measures the direction and extends of mismatch in the case of asset liability either by funding or through the maturity gap.

Duration model: The duration model is a primarily used for rate of interest and its impact on assets and liabilities as the duration model takes into consideration about the period of entering of the cash flows and the liabilities and maturity of the assets.

Value at risk: The value at risk refers to the maximum extent of the expected loss which a bank can tolerate over a horizon of the target.

Simulation: The simulation model aid to introduce a dynamic feature in the analysis of interest rate risk.” (WIKIPEDIA , n.d.)

LITERATURE REVIEW

In their paper “Performance of Indian Public Sector Banks and Private Sector Banks: A Comparative Study, author has stated that public banks must pay attention on their functioning. These banks should select borrower very cleverly and also public banks should decrease the NPA level. Sometimes the perspective of management also defines the risk profile of banks which further determines the liquidity and profitability trade-off.” (Sharma, June 2011)

Authors Dr. Anurag Singh & Ms. Priyanka Tandon in their paper – “A Study of Financial Performance: A Comparative Analysis of SBI and ICICI Bank” have discussed ALM’s importance as a risk management in commercial banks through an analysis of SBI & ICICI Banks. (SINGH & TANDON, 2012)

The author has analysed the effect of actions and approaches banks undertake to achieve the ideal alignment of assets & liabilities. The author has focused their research on understanding ALM techniques impact on Banks performance in general and profitability in particular. (Singh, 2013)

Amit Kumar Meena and Joydip Dhar in their paper – “An Empirical Analysis and Comparative Study of Liquidity Ratios and Asset-Liability Management of Banks Operating in India have focused on the analysis and comparison of liquidity ratios and asset liability management practiced in top three banks from public, private and foreign sector in India. The analysis was based upon the liquidity ratios calculation and the determination of maturity gap profiles for the banks under study. The results of this study suggested that overall banks in India have very good short term liquidity position and all banks were financing their short-term liabilities by their long-term assets.” (Dhar, 2014)

Md. Salim Uddin, & Anamul Haque in their paper – “The Impacts Of Asset Liability Management on Profitability Of Selected Banks In Bangladesh - There is no underlying fact to ignore the importance of asset-liability management policy to ensure profitability and long-run sustainability of financial institutions in any economy. The study has been conducted to investigate the impacts of ALM policy on the profitability of sample banks working in Bangladesh”. (Uddin & Haque, 2016)

“S. P. Joshi & Dr. R. V. Sontakay in their paper Review Paper on Asset Liability Management in Banking System”, have discussed the need for timely ALM analysis so as to survive in the market, by estimating the value of risk factors involved. “The survey helps for emerging banks to decide the different ALM process used by the banking industries and to select the efficient process out of the reported techniques”. (Sontakay, 2017)

RESEARCH DESIGN

Research Objective:

To understand the risk management techniques involved in ALM.

To analyse two selected private and public sector commercial banks using ALM.

Research Plan:

Data collection method: Secondary method

Research Sample:

Top four commercial banks are selected for this study:

Period of Study:

The period of this study is FY 2019-2020

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

Asset Liability Management is widely studied through gap analysis and this method is used in this paper. Gap analysis assess interest rate risk or liquidity risk faced by the institution. “The assets and liabilities which changes with change in interest rate are called as Rate Sensitive Assets (RSA) and Rate Sensitive Liabilities (RSL) respectively. These Rate Sensitive Assets and Liabilities are categorized into various maturity buckets as per RBI guidelines. All Assets and Liabilities are to be segregated as per their maturity profile into various maturity buckets:

- 1 day
- 2 days to 7 days
- 8 days to 14 days
- 15 days to 30 days
- 31 days and up to 2 months
- Over 2 months and up to 3 months
- Over 3 months and up to 6 months
- Over 6 months and up to 1 year
- Over 1 year and up to 3 years
- Over 3 year and up to 5 years
- Over 5 years” (RBI, n.d.)

The Gap between Rate Sensitive Assets and Liabilities under their respective time buckets is also called as Mismatch. To simplify the understanding of Maturity Gap Analysis, certain points are explained in the form of formula:

Rate Sensitive Assets = Advances + Investments

Rate Sensitive Liabilities = Deposits + Borrowings

Maturity GAP = Rate Sensitive Asset – Rate Sensitive Liabilities

Positive GAP = Rate Sensitive Asset > Rate Sensitive Liabilities

Negative GAP = Rate Sensitive Asset < Rate Sensitive Liabilities

Zero GAP = Rate Sensitive Asset = Rate Sensitive Liabilities

Maturity Mismatch % = (Mismatch ÷ Rate Sensitive Liabilities) × 100

Maturity GAP Ratio = Rate Sensitive Asset ÷ Rate Sensitive Liabilities

Table 1 - Total Rate Sensitive Assets

Maturity Gap Analysis					
Total RSA	1 day	2 to 7 days	8 to 14 days	15 to 30 days	31 days and upto 2 months
AXIS	39191.7	5890.15	8651.35	15347.11	19946.59
ICICI	43574.67	42712.76	12381.92	28360.06	29733.85
SBI	57,631.11	18,574.82	20,573.34	48,230.53	63,021.10
PNB	3554.79	7510.29	3790.62	16470.79	23894.28

Maturity Gap Analysis					
Over 2 and upto 3 months	Over 3 and upto 6 months	Over 6 months and upto 1 year	Over 1 and upto 3 years	Over 3 and upto 5 years	Over 5 years
18554.51	37062.53	61956.78	129976.31	76703.26	314878.19
32459.38	64218.73	96581.78	208360.69	139529.39	196908.22
77,808.90	1,20,348.82	1,86,511.61	12,64,855.00	3,64,892.61	11,49,796.24
22510.93	28524.54	41647.21	220037.22	56228.99	291412.17

Chart 1: Total RSA

The Rate sensitive assets are higher in the time bucket of over 1 year and up to 3 years; and over 5 years. The Banks are most likely focusing on Long term Investments. The interest rates must have been favourable for the banks in the long-term investments and loans. Rate sensitive assets become more profitable or less profitable as lending rates increase or decrease.

Table 3 -Total Rate Sensitive Liabilities

Maturity Gap Analysis					
Total RSL	1 day	2 to 7 days	8 to 14 days	15 to 30 days	31 days and upto 2 months
AXIS	9393.22	29836.99	15529.17	24900.52	35119.82
ICICI	10413.62	78834.46	17716.83	20503.79	27951.41
SBI	51328.2	102847.7	52391.44	92285.24	146934.61
PNB	14798.47	19026.16	17697.4	13459.07	22817.12

Maturity Gap Analysis					
Over 2 and upto 3 months	Over 3 and upto 6 months	Over 6 months and upto 1 year	Over 1 and upto 3 years	Over 3 and upto 5 years	Over 5 years
28824.06	71099.14	110115.57	74011.81	16471.78	372756.99
26068	61793.42	83338.29	125259.53	242943.37	239043.03
137785.8	357468.59	658868.44	671174.63	374006.75	911184.99
21396.37	48683.65	59317.92	141508.09	179632.07	215735.44

Chart 2: Total RSL

The Rate sensitive liabilities are higher in the time bucket in the range of 6 months to over 5 years. The Banks must be focusing on fixed interest rate liabilities as it involves steady payments over time as the interest rates on fixed-rate loans remains constant. This helps in creating and maintaining budgets for future reference.

Table 4: Gap or Mismatch in Assets and Liabilities

Maturity Gap Analysis					
GAP or Mismatch	1 day	2 to 7 days	8 to 14 days	15 to 30 days	31 days and upto 2 months
AXIS	29798.48	-23946.84	-6877.82	-9553.41	-15173.23
ICICI	33161.05	-36121.7	-5334.91	7856.27	1782.44
SBI	6302.91	-84272.83	-31818.1	-44054.71	-83913.51
PNB	-11243.68	-11515.87	-13906.78	3011.72	1077.16

Maturity Gap Analysis					
Over 2 and upto 3 months	Over 3 and upto 6 months	Over 6 months and upto 1 year	Over 1 and upto 3 years	Over 3 and upto 5 years	Over 5 years
-10269.6	-34036.61	-48158.79	55964.5	60231.48	-57878.8
6391.38	2425.31	13243.49	83101.16	-103413.98	-42134.81
-59976.9	-237119.8	-472356.83	593680.37	-9114.14	238611.25
1114.56	-20159.11	-17670.71	78529.13	-123403.08	75676.73

Chart 3: Gap or Mismatch

Maturity Gap in Asset Liability Management is the difference between Rate sensitive assets and Rate sensitive liabilities. The liabilities are exceeding the assets in the short-term period. It may indicate the banks inefficiency to utilize its assets in the short-term in an optimum manner. There may higher borrowings in this time period.

Table 5: Cumulative Gap or Mismatch in Assets and Liabilities

Maturity Gap Analysis					
Cumulative Mismatch	1 day	2 to 7 days	8 to 14 days	15 to 30 days	31 days and upto 2 months
AXIS	29798.48	5851.64	-1026.18	-10579.59	-25752.82
ICICI	33161.05	-2960.65	-8295.56	-439.29	1343.15
SBI	6302.91	-77969.92	-109788	-153842.7	-237756.2
PNB	-11243.68	-22759.55	-36666.33	-33654.61	-32577.45

Maturity Gap Analysis					
Over 2 and upto 3 months	Over 3 and upto 6 months	Over 6 months and upto 1 year	Over 1 and upto 3 years	Over 3 and upto 5 years	Over 5 years
-36022.4	-70058.98	-118217.77	-62253.27	-2021.79	-59900.59
7734.53	10159.84	23403.33	106504.49	3090.51	-39044.3
-297733	-534853	-1007209.8	-413529.41	-422643.55	-184032.3
-31462.9	-51622	-69292.71	9236.42	-114166.66	-38489.93

Chart 4: Cumulative Mismatch

Cumulative mismatch is the consolidation of the maturity gaps in Rate sensitive assets and Rate sensitive liabilities pertaining to all the time buckets. The negative gap is highest for SBI Bank in the period of 6 months to 1 year. All the other three banks have efficiently maintained their gap scenario well. Axis Bank, ICICI Bank and PNB have utilised their assets in an optimum manner.

Table 6: Gap or Mismatch (%) in Assets and Liabilities

Maturity Gap Analysis					
Mismatch %	1 day	2 to 7 days	8 to 14 days	15 to 30 days	31 days and upto 2 months
AXIS	317%	-80%	-44%	-38%	-43%
ICICI	318%	-46%	-30%	38%	6%
SBI	12%	-82%	-61%	-48%	-57%
PNB	-76%	-61%	-79%	22%	5%

Maturity Gap Analysis					
Over 2 and upto 3 months	Over 3 and upto 6 months	Over 6 months and upto 1 year	Over 1 and upto 3 years	Over 3 and upto 5 years	Over 5 years
-36%	-48%	-44%	76%	366%	-16%
25%	4%	16%	66%	-43%	-18%
-44%	-66%	-72%	88%	-2%	26%
5%	-41%	-30%	55%	-69%	35%

Chart 5: Mismatch %

$$\text{Mismatch \%} = \frac{\text{Mismatch or Gap}}{\text{Rate sensitive liabilities}} \times 100$$

Table 7: Gap or Mismatch Ratio in Assets and Liabilities

Table 7: Gap or Mismatch Ratio in Assets and Liabilities

Maturity Gap Analysis					
Mismatch ratio	1 day	2 to 7 days	8 to 14 days	15 to 30 days	31 days and upto 2 months
AXIS	4.17	0.20	0.56	0.62	0.57
ICICI	4.18	0.54	0.70	1.38	1.06
SBI	1.12	0.18	0.39	0.52	0.43
PNB	0.24	0.39	0.21	1.22	1.05

Maturity Gap Analysis					
Over 2 and upto 3 months	Over 3 and upto 6 months	Over 6 months and upto 1 year	Over 1 and upto 3 years	Over 3 and upto 5 years	Over 5 years
0.64	0.52	0.56	1.76	4.66	0.84
1.25	1.04	1.16	1.66	0.57	0.82
0.56	0.34	0.28	1.88	0.98	1.26
1.05	0.59	0.70	1.55	0.31	1.35

Chart 6: Mismatch Ratio

$$\text{Mismatch Ratio} = \frac{\text{Rate sensitive assets}}{\text{Rate sensitive liabilities}}$$

Axis Bank has the highest mismatch ratio i.e., 4.66 in the time bucket of over 3 years and up to 5 years. ICICI Bank follows with 4.18 in the short duration bucket of 1 day. SBI has 1.88 and PNB has 1.55 mismatch ratio in the same bracket of over 1 year and up to 3 years.

CONCLUSION:

The critical assessment of public and private banks shows that the both highest positive gap and negative gap is found in SBI in the maturity basket of over 1 and to 3 years and over 5 years maturity basket and in the maturity basket of over 3 months to 6 months and 6 months to 1 year while PNB, ICICI and Axis managing the gap effectively in all the maturity baskets. The positive mismatch % of approximately 317 and 318% with respect to RSL is appearing in shorter maturity basket (1 day) in Private sector banks and longer maturity basket (over 3 years and upto 5 years) in case of SBI which shows private banks are effective in managing longer maturity baskets and public sector banks are managing shorter maturity baskets effectively. The further analysis reveals that maturity Gap analysis is an effective technique for understanding and managing liquidity risks throughout the maturity brackets prescribed by RBI. Banks need to maintain the gap as low as possible in order to avoid any liquidity exposure and to maintain banks liquidity, profitability and solvency effectively.

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